

THE ROLE OF WRITS IN MODERN JUDICIAL SYSTEM

ABSTRACT

The judiciary is dynamically carving the principles and exceptions, while making the judicial review of administrative actions. The administrative law is that branch of law that keeps the governmental actions within the bounds of law or to put it negatively, it prevents the enforcement of blatantly bad orders from being derogatory. Judiciary exercising its control over governmental actions through Judicial review power. The judicial review of administrative actions in the form of writ jurisdiction is to ensure that the decisions taken by the authorities are legal, rational, proper, fair and reasonable. In Indian constitution provided prerogative writ jurisdiction to empower the Supreme Court and High court to issue such writs. Prerogative writs are a subset of writs, which are issued as an extraordinary remedy for aggrieved persons. It is a constitutional remedy available to a person to bring his complaint or grievance against any administrative action to the notice of the court. Safeguard of fundamental rights, other legal rights and to assurance of natural justice are the most important components of writ jurisdictions. The power to issue prerogative writs has been granted by the Constitution under Article 226 to the High Courts and to the Supreme Court under Article 32. Under the constitution of India there are five kinds of writs available, which can be opt by victim in different situations in accordance law. it is also important to note that there is a little bit difference between the Supreme Court and High Courts in case of application of writ Jurisdiction.

KEYWORDS

Writs, Prerogative writs, fundamental rights, legal rights.

INTRODUCTION

The Courts have constantly tried to protect the liberties of the people and assume powers under the Constitution for judicial review of administrative actions. The discretionary powers must be curbed, if they are misused or abused. There has been tremendous expansion in the administrative process. This is natural in a welfare state as a welfare state is basically an administrative state. So, expansion in the administrative power is a consequence of the concept of welfare state. All legal power, according to H.W.R. Wade, 'as opposed to duty, is inevitably discretionary to a greater or lesser extent. Therefore, to maintain rule of law it is necessary to control this discretionary element in the administrative power. Justice Douglas of the U.S. Supreme Court has rightly remarked that it is the majesty of the administrative law that it has been able to control absolute discretion on the part of the government or any ruler or official because absolute.

Source of Writs

The origin of writs can be drawn from the English Judicial system and were created with the development of English folk courts-moots to the common law courts. The law of writs has its origin from the orders passed by the King's Bench in England. Writs were issued on a petition presented to the king in council and were considered as a royal order. Writs were a written order issued in the name of the king which acted as groundwork for the subsequent proceedings. However, with different segments writs took various forms and names.

Historical Background

The origin of writs in India goes back to the Regulating Act, 1773 under which Supreme Court was established at Calcutta. The charter also established other High courts, and these High Courts had analogous power to issue writs as successor to the Supreme Court. The other courts which were established subsequently did not enjoy this power. The writ jurisdiction of these courts was limited to their original civil jurisdiction which they enjoyed under section 45 of the Specific Relief Act, 1877.

Writ and writ jurisdiction

In common law, a writ is a formal written order issued by a body with administrative or judicial jurisdiction; in modern usage, this body is generally a court. The concept of writ was first developed by the Anglo-Saxons in England. The Monarch would issue letters which held orders and directions. Since then, writs have been incorporated by various countries into their legal system. Generally, warrants, prerogative writs and subpoena are common type of writ but may form exist and have existed.³ In modern period all countries adopting democratic polity and welfare state concepts, where the administrative authorities are vested with vast discretionary powers. The exercise of those powers often becomes subjective in the absence of specific guidelines etc. Hence the need for a control of the discretionary powers is essential to ensure that 'rule of law' exist in all governmental actions. The judicial review of administrative actions in the form of writ jurisdiction is to ensure that the decisions taken by the authorities are legal, rational, proper, fair and reasonable. In Indian constitution provided prerogative writ jurisdiction to empower the Supreme Court and High court to issue such writs. Prerogative writs are a subset of writs, which are issued as an extraordinary remedy for aggrieved persons.

The power to issue prerogative writs has been granted by the Constitution under Article 226 to the High Courts and to the Supreme Court under Article 32. Further, the power to issue writs can also be extended to any other courts (including local courts) by Parliament via making a law for local limits of jurisdiction of such courts. Moreover, kindly note that Court Martial i.e. the tribunals established under the military law has been exempted from the writ jurisdiction of the Supreme Court and the high courts via article 33.

Article 32

Article 32 provides the right to Constitutional remedies which means that a person has right to move to Supreme Court for getting his/her fundamental rights protected. Article 32 makes the Supreme Court the defender and guarantor of the fundamental rights. Further, power to issue writs comes under original jurisdiction of the Supreme Court. This means that a person may approach SC directly for remedy rather than by way of appeal. It can be invoked only to get a remedy related to fundamental rights. It is not there for any other constitutional or legal right for which different laws are available. Further, it is made clear that right to move to Supreme Court cannot be suspended except otherwise provided by the Constitution. This implies that this right suspended during a national emergency. This Article 32 was called “the

soul of the constitution and very heart of it” by Dr. Ambedkar. Moreover, Supreme Court has included it in basic structure doctrine during its pronouncements.

Article 226

Article 226 can be invoked not only for the enforcement of Fundamental Rights but for ‘any other purpose’ as well. This means that the Supreme Court’s power under Article 32 is restricted as compared with the power of a High Court under Article 226, for, if an administrative action does not affect a Fundamental Right, then it can be challenged only in the High Court under Article 226, and not in the Supreme Court under Article 32. The words “for any other purpose” found in Article 226 (but not in Article 32), enable a High Court to take cognizance of any matter even if no Fundamental Rights are involved.

Difference between the Writ jurisdiction of Supreme Court and High Court

- While Supreme Court has power to issue writs via article 32, High Courts have this power via article 226.
- While Supreme Court has power to issue writs for enforcement of ONLY Fundamental rights, High Courts can issue writs for enforcement of fundamental rights as well as any other matter, where court felt. That a writ is a proper remedy in such a case. Thus, High Court has a wider jurisdiction from Supreme Court in matter of issuing writs.
- Supreme Court can issue a writ against any person or authority within the territory of India while high court can issue such writ under its own territorial jurisdiction. Thus, High court’s writ jurisdiction is narrower in terms of territorial extent. HC jurisdiction confines of the state and UTs to which its jurisdiction extends.
- Supreme Court benign guarantor or defender of fundamental rights it cannot refuse to exercise its writ jurisdiction under Article 32. In fact, Article 32 itself is a fundamental right so constitution imposes duty on SC to issue the writs. However, for high courts, exercising the power to issue writs is discretionary.

Writs available under Indian constitution

Writ of Habeas Corpus

The Latin term Habeas Corpus means **To have the body**. The incalculable value of habeas corpus is that it enables the immediate determination of the right of the appellant's freedom.

“The writ of Habeas Corpus is a process for securing liberty to the party for illegal and unjustifiable detention. It objects for providing a prompt and effective remedy against illegal restraints to protect the liberty and freedom which is conceived to be very vital. It is issued against the wrongful detention or confinement through the police authority. By virtue of this writ the police authorities or other such statutory authorities are empowered to bring the

custody of the person who has been wrongfully detained by the court of law. It is a judicial order issued by Supreme Court or High Court through which a person confined may secure his release. The writ of Habeas Corpus can be filed by any person on behalf of the other person. In *Devi v. Union of India*, the Supreme Court held that in a case of writ of Habeas corpus there are no strict observances of the rules of burden of proof. Even a post card by any pro bono public is satisfactory to galvanize the court into examining the legality of detention. In *A.D.M. Jabalpur v. Shivakanta Shukla*, it was observed that “the writ of Habeas Corpus is a process for securing the liberty of the subject by affording an effective means of immediate relief from unlawful or unjustifiable detention whether in prison or private custody. By it the High Court and the judges of that court at the instance of a subject aggrieved command the production of that subject and inquire into the cause of his imprisonment. If there is no legal justification for that detention, then the party is ordered to be released.” In the case of *State of Bihar v. Kameshwar Singh* it was stated that, the writ of Habeas Corpus is in the nature of an order for calling upon the person who has detained or arrested another person to produce the latter before the court, in order to let court know on what ground he has been confined and to set him free if there is no legal justification for the imprisonment. One of the telling ways in which the violation of that right can reasonably be prevented and due compliance with the mandate of article 21 secured, is to mulct its violators in the payment of monetary compensation.

Writ of Mandamus

Writs of Mandamus is a judicial remedy which is in the form of an order from a superior court to any Government agency, court or public authority to do or forbear from doing any specific act which that body is obliged to do under the law. The writ of mandamus is issued whenever the public authorities fail to perform the statutory duties conferred on them. Such writ is issued to perform the duties as provided by the state under the statute or forbear or restrain from doing any specific act. The first case reported on the writ of mandamus was the *Middleton* case in 1573 wherein a citizen's franchise was restored. The writ of mandamus can be issued if the public authority vested with power abuses the power or acts mala fide to it. In *Halsbury's Laws of England*, it is mentioned that, “As a general rule the order will not

be granted unless the party complained of has known what it was required to do, so that he had the means of considering whether or not he should comply, and it must be shown by evidence that there was a distinct demand of that which the party seeking the mandamus desires to enforce and that that demand was met by a refusal.” The writ of mandamus is ordered when the statutory authorities who entrusted with the duties fail to discharge its

obligatory duty. It may be applied when the government authorities vested with absolute powers fail to perform their administrative and statutory duties. In *Ratlam Municipal Council v. Virdiana*, on account of the public nuisance created in the area by the corporation in not maintaining the drainage system and the dirty water stinking had clogged around which obviously created nuisance at the hands of municipality for not discharging the duties under the act. As the residents of Ratlam municipality moved the

Sub-divisional magistrate under section 133 of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 for abatement of nuisance and the court issued the directions that, “Judicial discretion when facts for its exercise are present has a mandatory import. Therefore, when the Sub-Divisional Magistrate, Ratlam, has before him information and evidence which disclose the presence of public nuisance, considers it lawful to remove such obstruction. This is a public duty implicit in the public power to be exercised on behalf of the public and is pursuant to public proceeding.”

Writ of Certiorari

Certiorari is a Latin term being in the passive form of the word Certiorari meaning thereby “**to inform**”. It was a royal demand for information. Certiorari can be described as “one of the most valuable and efficient remedies.” Certiorari is one of the five prerogative writs adopted by the Indian Constitution under Article 226 which would be enforced against the decisions of the authority exercising judicial or quasi-judicial powers. Such powers are exercised when the authorities have failed to exercise the jurisdiction though vested in it or failed to exercise the jurisdiction though vested on him or to correct the apparent error on the face of record or there is violation of the principle of natural justice. An instance showing the certiorari powers was exercised by the Hon’ble Supreme court in *A.K. v. Union of India*, where the selection was challenged on the ground of bias. The Supreme Court delineated the distinction between quasi-judicial and administrative authority. The Supreme Court exercising its powers issued the writ of Certiorari for quashing the action. The writ of Certiorari is basically issued against the statutory bodies exercising judicial or quasi-judicial powers. Such writ is issued against the authorities namely the government and the courts or other statutory bodies who have power to determine and decide the issues between the parties. In deciding such issues if the decision-making order is passed without any authority or has passed the order in exercise of such authority or has committed an error of law and facts the high court is empowered to correct such error of the lower court or government authorities. Certiorari may apply when the administrative or executive authority fails to

observe their duty to act fairly with respect to the administrative functions. The writ of Certiorari may also be issued against a subordinate tribunal even if the decision impugned is pronounced. A leading case of *Ryots of Farabundo vs Zemindari* was the first decision on the writ of Certiorari.

Writ of Prohibition

The writ of Prohibition is issued by the court exercising the power and authorities from continuing the proceedings as basically such authority has no power or jurisdiction to decide the case. Prohibition is an extra ordinary prerogative writ of a preventive nature. The underlying principle is that prevention is better than cure." In *East India Commercial Co. Ltd v. Collector of Customs*, a writ of prohibition is an order directed to an inferior Tribunal forbidding it from continuing with a proceeding therein on the ground that the proceeding

without or more than jurisdiction or contrary to the laws of the land, statutory or otherwise. The writ of Prohibition is issued essentially against the government or its authorities when they are not conferred with the power or jurisdiction to decide the dispute. The court by virtue of this power restrains the authority to exercise such powers which are not given to the authority.

Writ of Quo Warranto

Quo Warranto means "**by what warrant or authority**". Quo Warranto writ is issued against the person of public who occupies the public seat without any qualification for the appointment. It is issued to restrain the authority or candidate from discharging the functions of public office. In *University of Mysore v. Govinda Rao*, the Supreme Court observed that the procedure of quo Warranto confers the jurisdiction and authority on the judiciary to control executive action in making the appointments to public offices against the relevant statutory provisions; it also protects a citizen being deprived of public office to which he may have a right. The high Court would exercise the power of Quo Warranto against the public authority or government who acts contrary to the provisions of the statute and restrains the authority or public servant from usurping the public office on account of lack of qualification. It is a means of asserting sovereign right. In *Sonu Sampat v. Jalgaon Borough Municipality*, "If the appointment of an officer is illegal, every that he acts in that office, a fresh cause of action arises and there can be therefore no question of delay in presenting a petition for quo warranto in which his very, right to act in such a responsible post has been questioned."

CONCLUSION

In our country the judiciary or law is supreme. Writ jurisdictions are judicial reviews of administrative actions. Judiciaries always stand to ensure that all administrative actions are confined to the limits of the law. Thus, the writ jurisdictions act as judicial restraints of policy decisions which are unreasonable, unfair and against public interests. In recent years, as the incumbents of Parliament have become less representative of the will of the people, there has been a growing sense of public frustration with the democratic process. That is why the higher judiciary had to expand its jurisdiction by, at times, issuing novel directions to the executive by issuing Writs, which many scholars describing as judicial activism. “So long as we may have an Independent Judiciary, the great interests of the people will be safe” – John Rutledge.

REFERENCE

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